

Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is a Short Range Interaction

O Manor

June 17, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the spin of gravity, it is evident that it is not a long ranged field but rather a short ranged, similar to the strong force. Such a claim is supported by the coupling constants series and the transition from spin representation to net variation representation. Additional support to the lack of GR as a sufficient theory is the fact that it only includes fermions clusters while ignoring the bosonic fields in its innate description.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (1.21)$$

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow 2N(g) \quad (1.31)$$

How can gravity mediate the relationship between the sun and the earth if the graviton was not detected? Not even a single particle of it was detected near the earth. That is a major flaw in Einstein theory and in the current ideas describing gravity. Gravity in modern theories refer to the graviton as the generator to a long range, it does not refer to bosonic fields but rather only to fermion clusters as a cause. That is an inaccurate picture of what nature is doing, according to the coupling constants series.

However, even if GR was to refer to bosonic fields, gravity cannot mediate the interaction long range due to its spin two. Spin two is synonymous with three net variations combine, with additional element (3), yielding an even number, which vanish. The end result is a short range interaction similar to the strong, which has only one term in the coupling series. The conclusion is that gravity might be responsible for the formation of matter, but as mentioned above, it can not mediate the interaction at long range scale, it's impossible, not the graviton. In addition, the fact it was not found is a positive validation of that claim.

According to the new framework the photons are net curvature on the manifold, that is how the coupling constant series was derived, in particular that was theorized in theorem (2) before the coupling constant was derived. The photons propagating long ranged due to their spin one, they add up to a positive summation by equation (1.3) and causing the curvature in long-range scales. Einstein theory does not refer to bosons in the context of gravity, only to large-scale matter clusters. Another flaw in Einstein theory is that it does not explain how does matter clusters were formed in the first place, i.e. galaxies and clusters of galaxies, and the answer is already given in the 8T.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.32)$$

While in Einstein theory, gravity is associated to fermionic clusters which in the 8T are described by the term:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.33)$$

Which proved to vanish into matter, by threefold combinations of two distinct elements. The 8T is different in two major ways from GR, despite it is built originally on the Einstein manifold, which in the theory was invoked stationary. The first is it takes into account insights of the coupling constants series in its first and second representation and so predict the graviton as a short-range force. The second and the main point, it that the bosonic propagations are adding up to a net curvature on the metric, creating the gravitational effect and ensuring the earth will circle the sun, that was the idea behind the construction of the coupling terms and how the fine structure constant was derived. Such an idea is suitable as mentioned in previous paper, for the rapid formation of galaxies. The desired conclusion is that quantum gravity and Einstein gravity are very different, at quantum scale things get more complex and spin must be taken into account in consideration of the gravitational effect.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "8T: Rapid Galaxies formation" In: (2021)